

Securing User Authenticity with PAN Card Verification and Text Extraction using CNN and Tesseract

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Abstract—This paper introduces a novel methodology for PAN card authentication and text extraction employing Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) in tandem with the Tesseract Optical Character Recognition (OCR) engine. The proposed system is tailored to authenticate government documents submitted by users, ensuring their credibility and integrity. Leveraging CNN, the system accurately discerns specified documents, bolstering the assurance of data reliability. Post validation, Tesseract seamlessly extracts pertinent information from the identified documents. This integrated approach yields an effective and dependable solution for automating document verification and data extraction processes. The research bears significant implications for streamlining administrative procedures and advancing document-centric workflows in diverse sectors.

Keywords—Image classification, Computer vision, Optical Character Recognition (OCR), Pre-processing, Neural Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's digitized landscape, the accurate identification and validation of government-issued documents are essential for various administrative processes. Among these, the Permanent Account Number (PAN) card is of paramount importance, serving as a primary identification document for eliminates the need for human intervention, enabling them to adapt and recognize intricate patterns in images. This intrinsic capability makes CNNs particularly adept in computer vision tasks, where extracting meaningful information from complex visual data is paramount.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) excel at invariant feature learning, identifying objects despite scale, orientation, or lighting variations. Their parallel processing architecture makes them highly scalable for large image datasets. Unlike SVMs, which rely on predefined features, CNNs are adept at handling intricate visual data. Random Forests, while interpretable, may oversimplify complex patterns, missing fine-grained details captured by CNNs. CNNs showcase adaptability through techniques like transfer learning, outperforming Linear models that assume linear relationships. With their hierarchical feature learning, CNNs

financial transactions. This paper endeavors to introduce a pioneering approach for the classification of PAN cards and the extraction of relevant text information. This process is accomplished through the synergistic application of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and the Tesseract Optical Character Recognition (OCR) engine.

The decision to leverage Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) is grounded in their proven efficacy in image classification tasks. CNNs excel in discerning intricate patterns and features within images, making them highly proficient in the nuanced task of distinguishing PAN cards from other documents. This approach sets itself apart from alternative classification algorithms like Support Vector Machines (SVM) or Random Forests, as it inherently learns hierarchical representations directly from the image data.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) stand out as a superior choice in scenarios where nuanced visual information is crucial for precise classification, outperforming algorithms like Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Random Forests. Unlike traditional methods that rely on manual feature engineering, CNNs autonomously learn relevant features from raw data.

discern intricate patterns, giving them an edge over linear models. As computational resources advance, CNNs become even more powerful, solidifying their place in image analysis and computer vision across diverse industries and research fields.

Tesseract's dominance in OCR stems from its unique advantages. As an open-source tool, it fosters a dynamic developer community, ensuring continuous improvement and adaptability, a rarity in proprietary solutions. Its cross-platform compatibility and extensive language support, even for complex scripts, set it apart. Tesseract's adaptive learning and robust preprocessing handle diverse fonts and layouts adeptly, a challenge for many OCR engines. It offers versatile output formats, surpassing tools with limited options. Continual refinement by a dedicated developer community keeps Tesseract at the forefront. Its customizability,

combined with commercial support options, further solidify its leading position in OCR.

Upon successful classification of PAN cards, the integration of the Tesseract OCR engine seamlessly bridges the gap between document identification and information extraction. Tesseract's robust optical character recognition capabilities facilitate the extraction of pertinent textual information, further enhancing the system's automation and efficiency.

This integrated approach not only revolutionizes the process of PAN card verification but also holds broader implications for streamlining administrative procedures and advancing document-centric workflows across diverse sectors. The subsequent sections of this paper delve into the intricacies of the methodology, present experimental results, and provide a comprehensive analysis of its impact on document processing and administrative efficiency.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

K. Patnaik et. al [2] Explores the application of Tesseract LSTM, an OCR technique that leverages Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for precise text extraction from images.

Martínek et. al [3] Presents techniques for conducting OCR on historical document images with limited real-world data, placing a strong emphasis on the efficient extraction of text from these documents

Deepa [4] presents a framework encompassing Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for image classification.

Mingyuan Xin et. al [5] proposed a novel training criterion for deep neural networks to optimize maximum interval minimum classification error. Simultaneously, a synergistic analysis and fusion of cross entropy and M3 CE metrics enhances overall performance.

Qixiang Ye et. al [6] analyzes technical challenges, methods, and performance of text detection and recognition in color imagery

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) represent a paradigm shift in image processing. These deep learning models excel in discerning intricate patterns, shapes, and features within images. Their hierarchical architecture enables them to learn complex representations directly from image data. CNNs have become instrumental in tasks like image classification and feature extraction.

Tesseract, an open-source OCR engine, has been a cornerstone in text extraction tasks. Its proficiency lies in recognizing characters and words across various fonts and styles. It employs classical computer vision techniques to accomplish this task. Tesseract's widespread adoption stems from its versatility and effectiveness in extracting textual information from a diverse range of images.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system introduces a cutting-edge methodology for document authentication and text extraction. It leverages the power of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) in conjunction with the Tesseract Optical Character Recognition (OCR) engine. This integrated approach aims to revolutionize the way government documents are verified and processed. By employing CNN, the system can accurately identify specified documents, significantly enhancing the assurance of data reliability. After validation, Tesseract seamlessly extracts relevant information from the identified documents. This automation not only ensures efficiency but also minimizes the potential for human error.

The system is specifically tailored to authenticate government documents submitted by users, ensuring their credibility and integrity. One pivotal document in focus is the Permanent Account Number (PAN) card, a critical identification document for financial transactions. By applying CNN and OCR in tandem, the system achieves a level of precision and efficiency that surpasses conventional methods. Fig. 1 Shows the normal work flow of the proposed system. We have deployed the deep learning model in Amazon Web Services (AWS) as an flask app service in one of its EC2 instance which enables seamless access and we can remotely access the model from anywhere. Also, we can use the service in almost all applications.

Fig. 1. Work flow of the proposed system.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

In this system, our objective is to verify and extract user information from provided cards. Specifically, we focus on validating PAN cards and extracting the relevant textual data. The various steps that included in the process are listed below.

A. Installing tools

In the pursuit of advancing research methodologies, the integration of powerful toolsets becomes paramount. This installation introduces four critical components that collectively augment the capabilities of image processing and text recognition endeavours installation follow-ups are shown

in Fig. 2. Firstly, Tesseract, an open-source OCR engine, unfurls new possibilities in text extraction from images, providing a robust foundation for document analysis. Secondly, TensorFlow, a preeminent deep learning framework, empowers researchers with the ability to construct and train neural networks, opening avenues for complex visual tasks. Complementing this, OpenCV, a versatile computer vision library, furnishes a suite of tools for image analysis, from basic manipulations to advanced object recognition. Lastly, NumPy, a cornerstone of numerical computing, underpins mathematical operations crucial in both image processing and machine learning. Together, these tools establish a cohesive ecosystem, equipping researchers with the means to unravel intricate insights from visual data, thereby propelling the boundaries of research across diverse disciplines.

```
#install tesseract
!pip install tesseract
#install tensorflow
!pip install tensorflow
#install opencv
!pip install opencv-python-headless
#install numpy
!pip install numpy

[ ] import os
import cv2
import numpy as np
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Flatten, Dense
from keras.callbacks import EarlyStopping
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from keras.regularizers import l2
from keras.layers import Dropout
from keras.models import load_model
```

Fig. 2. Installing and importing libraries

B. Data Collection and Preprocessing

In this initial phase, raw images of PAN cards and other documents are gathered and organized into a structured dataset. The preprocess images function systematically reads and resize images, ensuring uniformity in dimensions for effective processing. It also performs essential data augmentation techniques, such as normalization to a range of [0, 1], preparing the datasets for subsequent model training.

C. Data Splitting for Training and Testing

The datasets are divided into training and testing sets to facilitate robust evaluation of the model. This division is crucial in order to assess the model's generalization capabilities on unseen data. The split is performed with an 80-20 ratio, ensuring a substantial portion is allocated for testing, while still maintaining an adequate size for training.

```
# Split the data into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(images, labels, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

Fig. 3. Split the data into training and testing sets

D. Constructing the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

The CNN architecture excels in learning intricate features from input images through a series of Convolutional and max-pooling layers. These layers play a vital role in capturing features of varying complexities in a hierarchical manner. Additionally, L2 regularization with a weight decay factor of 0.001 is employed to mitigate overfitting and bolster model generalization.

The initial dense layer, comprising 128 units and activated by ReLU, is pivotal in feature acquisition. Subsequently, the output layer utilizes SoftMax activation, making it suitable for multi-class classification. The integration of L2 regularization (0.001) further fortifies the model against overfitting.

```
# Step 2: Build the CNN model with L2 regularization
model = Sequential()
model.add(Conv2D(16, (3, 3), activation='relu', input_shape=(224, 224, 3), kernel_regularizer=l2(0.001)))
model.add(MaxPooling2D((2, 2)))
model.add(Conv2D(32, (3, 3), activation='relu', kernel_regularizer=l2(0.001)))
model.add(MaxPooling2D((2, 2)))
model.add(Conv2D(64, (3, 3), activation='relu', kernel_regularizer=l2(0.001)))
model.add(MaxPooling2D((2, 2)))
model.add(Conv2D(128, (3, 3), activation='relu', kernel_regularizer=l2(0.001)))
model.add(MaxPooling2D((2, 2)))
model.add(Flatten())
model.add(Dense(128, activation='relu', kernel_regularizer=l2(0.001)))
model.add(Dense(len(class_labels), activation='softmax', kernel_regularizer=l2(0.001)))
```

Fig. 4. Build the CNN model with L2 regularization

E. Compiling the Model

The model is compiled using the Adam optimizer and sparse categorical cross-entropy loss function. This combination is well-suited for multi-class classification tasks like PAN card detection. The model's performance will be evaluated based on both loss and accuracy metrics during training.

F. Implementing Early Stopping

Early stopping is a critical component of the training process. It monitors the validation loss and halts training when no significant improvement is observed over a defined number of epochs (in this case, 15). This prevents overfitting and ensures that the model's performance is optimized.

G. Model Training and Evaluation

The model is trained on the pre-processed training data while periodically evaluating its performance on the validation set. This iterative process continues for a maximum of 100 epochs or until early stopping criteria are met. Due to the early stopping technique that implemented in this project the model training will stop whenever an overfitting occurs. The test accuracy we obtained is 97.17% with a test loss of 22.54%. The figures Fig. 6 & Fig. 7 is a graphical representation of the evaluation result.

```

Epoch 16/30
23/23 [=====] - 27s 1s/step - loss: 0.1634 - accuracy: 0.9822 - val_loss: 0.2709 - val_accuracy: 0.9454
Epoch 17/30
23/23 [=====] - 31s 1s/step - loss: 0.1388 - accuracy: 0.9877 - val_loss: 0.3523 - val_accuracy: 0.9180
23/23 [=====] - 30s 1s/step - loss: 0.1273 - accuracy: 0.9891 - val_loss: 0.3297 - val_accuracy: 0.9399
23/23 [=====] - 26s 1s/step - loss: 0.1238 - accuracy: 0.9959 - val_loss: 0.2785 - val_accuracy: 0.9563
Epoch 20/30
23/23 [=====] - 27s 1s/step - loss: 0.1053 - accuracy: 0.9945 - val_loss: 0.2895 - val_accuracy: 0.9290
Epoch 21/30
23/23 [=====] - 26s 1s/step - loss: 0.1150 - accuracy: 0.9918 - val_loss: 0.3046 - val_accuracy: 0.9344
Epoch 22/30
23/23 [=====] - 28s 1s/step - loss: 0.1326 - accuracy: 0.9822 - val_loss: 0.3368 - val_accuracy: 0.9290
Epoch 23/30
23/23 [=====] - 27s 1s/step - loss: 0.1487 - accuracy: 0.9713 - val_loss: 0.2622 - val_accuracy: 0.9617
Epoch 24/30
23/23 [=====] - 28s 1s/step - loss: 0.1278 - accuracy: 0.9904 - val_loss: 0.3011 - val_accuracy: 0.9563
Epoch 25/30
23/23 [=====] - 28s 1s/step - loss: 0.1099 - accuracy: 0.9932 - val_loss: 0.4596 - val_accuracy: 0.9180
6/6 [=====] - 2s 271ms/step - loss: 0.2255 - accuracy: 0.9617
Test Loss: 0.22545188665390015
Test Accuracy: 0.9617486596107483
    
```

Fig. 5. Evaluation result of the trained model

Fig. 6. Graphical representation of model accuracy

Fig. 7. Graphical representation of model loss

H. Processing image for text extraction

Now we convert a color image represented in the BGR color space to grayscale. This transformation is achieved using the OpenCV library (`cv2`) in Python. The variable `img` contains the original image, and `img_gray` will store the resulting grayscale version. Grayscale images are single-channel representations where pixel values denote intensity levels. This conversion is often beneficial for tasks that do not rely on color information, such as edge detection or OCR (Optical Character Recognition).

```

# Convert to grayscale
img_gray = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
    
```

Fig. 8. Converting image to grey scale image

I. Extracting text data from the PAN card

The code utilizes the `pytesseract` library for Optical Character Recognition (OCR) in Python. It processes a grayscale image `img\_gray`. The function `image\_to\_data` extracts text data, returning it in dictionary format. This structured output enables convenient access and manipulation of the recognized text and its attributes. In this paper we specifically extracting the PAN unique ID and the date of birth of the user.

```
data = pytesseract.image_to_data(img_gray, output_type='dict')
```

Fig. 9. Text extraction using Tesseract

J. Results

The anticipated outcome involves a two-step process. Initially, it entails classifying the provided image into its respective category. Subsequently, it involves the extraction of crucial data from images that meet the criteria of being valid. This dual-step approach ensures a comprehensive and precise analysis of the provided visual information. We are providing an image of pan card as data which is directly fed into the trained model using the CNN. Which classifies the image if it is valid or not. If the card is not valid then the data is not extracted. If valid then the data is extracted from the card. The Fig. 10. Show the prediction of particular class for the given card.

Fig. 10. Result obtained after prediction

K. Box plotting

Box plots, also known as box-and-whisker plots, are a commonly used graphical representation in machine learning and statistics to visualize the distribution and summary statistics of a datasets. They provide a concise way to depict the central tendency, spread, and potential outliers within a dataset. Box plots are particularly useful for understanding the distribution of numerical data, making them a valuable tool in various aspects of machine learning, including data analysis, model evaluation, and feature selection. In Fig. 11 the area that we are extracting is plotted.

Fig. 11. Box plotting the area we are extracting

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces an innovative method using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Tesseract OCR for authenticating government documents, with a focus on PAN cards. This approach improves document validation in digital administrative processes. Leveraging CNNs, our system accurately classifies documents, enhancing data integrity. Tesseract then extracts key information, automating verification and data extraction. This research promises to streamline administrative workflows across sectors.

CNNs excel in discerning patterns in images, making them ideal for differentiating PAN cards. Their adaptability and feature extraction capabilities set them apart from other algorithms like SVM or Random Forests. Comprehensive pre-processing and L2 regularization fortify the CNN model's performance. Integration with Tesseract bridges document identification and information extraction, enhancing automation. This integrated approach not only transforms PAN card verification but also streamlines administrative procedures across sectors. The paper delves into methodology, presents results, and analyses its impact. This research marks a significant step towards automating administrative workflows.

VII. FUTURE WORKS

Building upon the findings of this study, there is considerable potential for further research and development. One notable avenue is the expansion of the system's capabilities to classify and process various types of government ID cards beyond the scope of the current study. This extension can significantly enhance the system's versatility and practicality, making it a more valuable tool for real-world applications.

Another promising area for future development involves enhancing the system's user validation functionality. This can be achieved by implementing advanced image recognition techniques that validate the authenticity of individuals by cross-referencing their facial features with the images on their government-issued ID cards. By improving the accuracy and security of user validation, the system can be better equipped to meet stringent security requirements and can be applied in contexts where stringent identity verification is paramount.

VIII. REFERENCES

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